

Research Article

Management of *Sitophilus zeamais* Motshulsky (Coleoptera: Ciurculionidae) and *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) (Lepidoptera: Gelechidae) using Locally Available Inert Materials in Southern Ethiopia

Mesele Gemu^{1*}, Emana Getu², Abdurazak Yosuf³ and Tesfaye Tadess¹

¹Entomologist at Awassa Agricultural Research Center, P.O.Box 06, Awassa, Ethiopia.

²Addis Ababa University, Science Faculty, Biology Department, P.O.Box 1176, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

³Professor of Nematology at Alemaya Univeristy, P.O.Box 138, Dire Dawa, Ethiopia.

ARTICLE INFO

Article No.: 052213635

DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2013.6.052213635

Submitted: 22/05/2013

Accepted: 22/06/2013

Published: 29/06/2013

*Corresponding Author

Mesele Gemu

E-mail: Meselegemu

@yahoo.com

Phone: 251-046-2204521/251-

046-2200084,

Tel: 251-046-2202034/251-046-

2202050

ABSTRACT

Locally available inert materials including sawdust, coffee husk and wood ash were evaluated at different proportions against *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Sitotroga cerealella* in 2002 in Awassa National Maize Project entomology laboratory. The experiment was laid out incompletely Randomized design (CRD) in three replications. The insect pests were reared at laboratory condition before introducing into each treatment to obtain the same age group. Maize grain was disinfected to eliminate undesirable field infestation in refrigerator at -2°C before using for experimental purpose. The Treatments were 10%, 15%, 20% and 30% of coffee husk, 10%, 15%, 20% and 30% of saw dust, 10%, 15%, 20% and 30% of wood ash and 2% of Pirimiphos-methyl as standard check and untreated control. The efficacy of each treatment was evaluated with respect F1 progeny emergence of the pests, mean number of damaged kernels and germination percentage of maize kernels. Coffee husk and wood ash at all dosages were found to be effective in controlling *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella*. Wood ash at all proportions gave the best control of the pests during the study period. Wood ash and coffee husk at higher rates were more effective in controlling the pests. Sawdust at all dosages was not different from the untreated control in controlling *S. zeamais*. However, sawdust at some dosages showed superior performance against *S. cerealella*.

Keywords:

Inert materials, Coffee husk, *S. cerealella*, *S. zeamais*

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is the most important food crop grown in Africa and is capable of giving high yield (Assefa, 1981). Ethiopia produces more of maize than any other crop. The total area under maize cultivation in 2009/2010 was 1.69 hectares from which 37.8 million quintals of maize were produced which was higher than that of any other cereal crop (CSA, 2010), which also was more than 27 per cent of country's total grain production. Maize is major food crop of southern region of Ethiopia.

In the store maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky and *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) are the most serious cosmopolitan pest of stored cereal grain, especially of maize, in tropical and sub-tropical regions (Throne, 1994). Farmers in Africa in generally store their maize in open granaries. In recent years, post-harvest losses by these storage insect pests, have been recognized as an increasingly important problem in Africa (Markham et al., 1994), which urges developing a cheap and effective methods for reducing damage of stored grain maize in these countries.

Numerous coleopterous and lepidopterous pests attack maize in storage in Ethiopia (Emana, 1993; Firdissa and Abraham, 1999). Emana (1993) recorded eight insect species belonging to four orders and seven families on stored maize grain in Sidama administrative region namely, *S. cerealella*, *S. zeamais* Motschulsky, *Ephestia cautella* (Walker), *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst), *Tribolium confusum* Jaluelin de val, *Plodia interpunctella* (Hubner), *Rhizopertha dominica* (F.) and *Liposcelis* sp., of which *S. cerealella* and *S. zeamais* are the most important primary pests.

Both *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella* are pest of maize in the field and storage. Female *S. cerealella* can deposit 80 to 200 eggs on the outside of the kernel and the newly hatched larvae bore into the kernel (Mason, 2010). The larva completes its development inside the kernel until adult emergences. Unlike other grains, on kernels of maize two or three larvae may develop. There are three larval molts. The last larval instar usually spins a silken cocoon within the feeding cavity. The pupal case can be reddish brown to nearly black, depending on age. Adults emerge through a small round hole in the kernel. Upon adult emergence, females move to a surface above the food to release the sex pheromone. Males are attracted to this pheromone for mating. The female of *S. zeamais* lay eggs inside the grain followed by sealing of the hole with a secretion (Hill, 1983). The author added that in each hole a single egg is deposited and it is oval in shape and white in color. The total number of eggs laid per female ranges between 150 and 400 (Appert, 1987). However, female *S. zeamais* tended to cluster eggs on the grains and aggregated more eggs on lower grain quantities than on higher grain quantities (Danho et al., 2002).

In the store, maize insect pests cause losses ranging from 20 to 30 per cent in Ethiopia (Abraham, 1991; Emana, 1993). In *Bako* area, farmers reported 25 to 33 per cent maize grain losses within six months of storage period. In Sidama administrative region, 30 to 90 per cent losses could occur to maize grain stored for five to seven months (Emana, 1993). A number of experiments have been done on the management of storage pests at the farm storage level (Emana, 1999). Chemical control of insect pests has been the most efficient and effective means of protection of stored product (Emana, 1999). However, with the increasing cost of organic chemicals and their hazards to the environment, alternative control strategies are being exploited. One of the alternative control strategies is the use of locally available inert materials. Inert materials such as wood ash and similar fine substances are used in the control of storage pests by filling the space between maize kernels (Emana 1993; Gwinner *et al.*, 1996). This means that newly hatched insect pests are denied of their activities. They experience more difficulty in finding partners and as result are forced to deposit their entire stock of eggs on relatively few maize kernels. In general, identifying useful locally available inert materials against *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella* may provide important component of storage pest management in maize grain in Southern Ethiopia. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of locally available inert materials including coffee husk for the control of *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella* in Southern Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Establishment of culture of *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella*

S. zeamais

Adult *S. zeamais* of known age were produced in a sufficient number for the experiment following the rearing procedures of Strong and Subur (1968). About 25 kg of maize variety BH540 was cleaned to remove kernels with visible damage symptom and stored in a freezer at 0 to -2°C for one month to further clean the kernels from possible internal infestation (Strong *et al.*, 1967). Grain moisture content was measured by moisture tester. Low moisture level was adjusted to 12.5 per cent by adding water, while high moisture level was adjusted to 12.5 per cent by allowing it to dry slowly (Wright *et al.*, 1989).

Unsexed *S. zeamais* adults were collected from grain store of Awassa Agricultural Research Center and Debub University, the then Awassa College of Agriculture, and cultured on cleaned and disinfested maize in four replications. In each replication, 800 *S. zeamais* adults per 400 grams of grain were put in glass jar of three-liter capacity and covered with muslin cloth and fixed by rubber band. After seven days of oviposition period, all parent *S.*

zeamais adults were removed from each replication and placed on another set of grain in the same condition. Such removal of parent *S. zeamais* adults and placement on a fresh grain medium was made three times, so that sufficient number of laboratory reared *S. zeamais* adults of known age were made available.

After the third transfer, parent *S. zeamais* adults were discarded. Then each grain lot where *S. zeamais* adults oviposited for seven days was kept for progeny emergence. Starting from 34 days after infestation of the maize grain in the different batches, counts of emerged adults were recorded daily until the 45th day and those emerged on the same day were transferred to a glass jar of one liter capacity, so that each jar will contain *S. zeamais* adults of the same age. For the experiments, *S. zeamais* adults of known age were used.

S. cerealella

A new culture of *S. cerealella* was established by using maize kernels with 300 *S. cerealella* pupae as moths, which were collected from Debub University, the then called Awassa College of Agriculture, and put in three liters capacity jar containing 1.5 kilograms disinfested maize kernels (Emana, 1993 and 1999). A total of four jars were used for culture establishment. After disinfesting maize kernels at 0 to -2°C, it was stored in the laboratory under room temperature in a clean three-liter capacity jar. Then maize with 300 *S. cerealella* pupae were introduced to lay eggs on the disinfested kernels. After nineteen days of introduction, all live and dead moths were removed from the jar. The jars were inspected on daily bases for recording emergence of F1 moths. Then maize kernels with *S. cerealella* pupae, which emerged as F1 moth, were used for experimental purpose.

Use of Locally Available Inert Materials

S. zeamais

The local materials tested against *S. zeamais* include coffee husk, wood ash and sawdust. For each treatment, five hundred disinfested sound kernels were used in three liters capacity plastic bag and admixed at different proportions with different materials. Primiphos-methyl 2% dust at the rate of 10 ppm, as a standard check and the untreated control were included in the experiment for comparison.

Fourteen sexed and ten-to-fourteen-day-old *S. zeamais* adults were introduced into each treatment. Then plastic bags were pin-holed to ensure adequate aeration and folded and stapled from top to prevent escape of *S. zeamais* adults. The experiment was done under ambient laboratory conditions.

Parent *S. zeamais* adults' mortality was assessed after one, two, three and four weeks after treatment application and dead adult insects were counted and removed during each assessment. At 28th day after the infestation, the remaining *S. zeamais*

adults (dead and alive) were counted and removed together. The assessment periods were selected based on the earlier report by Dobie (1974).

After removing dead and live *S. zeamais* adults, the treatment remained under the same conditions to assess F1 progenies emergence. The F1 progeny of *S. zeamais* adults were removed and counted as soon as they emerged. This was continued up to 76 days according to Dobie (1974), Evans (1985) and Hodges and Meik (1986). At the end, weight loss of grain and number of damaged kernels were recorded by separating the admixture by winnowing in each treatment. Germination percentage of the grain was assessed by randomly picking one hundred kernels from each treatment and placing it on moist filter paper and kept for seven days. The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) in three replications.

S. cerealella

The local materials tested against *S. cerealella* include different proportions of coffee husk, wood ash and sawdust. For each treatment, five hundred disinfested sound kernels were used in three liters capacity plastic bag and admixed at different proportions with different materials. Primiphos-methyl 2% dust at the rate of 10 ppm as a standard check and the untreated control were included in the experiment for comparison. Twenty maize kernels with unsexed 20 pupae of *S. cerealella* were introduced into each treatment. Then plastic bags were pin-holed to ensure adequate aeration and folded and stapled from top to prevent escape of moths. The experiment was done under ambient condition.

Parent adult moths' mortality was assessed after one, two and three weeks after treatment application and the remaining dead and live moths were discarded together from the treatment at 21st day. Then, the treatment was kept under similar conditions to F1 progenies assessment. The F1 progeny of moths were counted and removed as soon as they were emerged. This continued up to 3 months. At the end, weight loss of grain and number of damaged kernels were recorded by separating the admixture by winnowing. Germination percentage of the kernels was assessed by randomly picking one hundred kernels from each treatment and placing it on moist filter paper and kept for seven days. The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) in three replications.

Per cent grain weight loss for all of the above experiments was calculated using Anon (1969) method. At the end of each experiment maize kernels were separated into two categories (undamaged and damaged) from each treatment. Grains in each category were counted and weighed separately and subjected to the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Weight loss} = \frac{(W_u \times N_d) - (W_d \times N_u)}{W_u \times (N_d + N_u)} \times 100$$

Where,

W_u = Weight of undamaged grains

N_u = Number of undamaged grains

W_d = Weight of damaged grains

N_d = Number of damaged grains

Data Analysis

Data on number of F1 emerged *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella* adults, number of damaged maize kernels and weight loss of grain were transformed before being subjected to statistical analysis. The data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance using MSTATC computer program and means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

S. zeamais

The effects of inert materials in the control of *S. zeamais* are presented in (Table 1). Among inert materials tested against the pest, wood ash at all dosages showed superior performance in all parameters compared to the untreated check. Sawdust at four dosages was not better than the untreated control in all parameters. Very few F1 progeny emerged from kernels treated with all dosages of wood ash. However, higher dosages of wood ash were found to be more effective in suppressing development of F1 progeny. Lowest number of F1 progeny emerged from maize kernels treated with 15 per cent w/w wood ash, while highest F1 progeny emerged from kernels treated with sawdust at 20 per cent w/w. Coffee husk relatively at higher dosages, 20 and 30 per cent w/w was found to be more effective in impeding the development of F1 progeny compared to the untreated control. Moreover, coffee husks in solid residue can be used animal feed, direct use as fuel, fermentation for the production of enzymes, citric acid, flavoring substances and as a substrate for growth of mushrooms (Gouvea et al., 2009).

There were significant differences in germination capacity of maize kernels treated with different inert materials and the untreated control. The highest germination percentage was recorded from kernels treated with wood ash 30 per cent w/w, while the lowest percentage was obtained from kernels treated with sawdust 30 per cent w/w (Fig. 1).

The results of the present study agree with reports of previous workers. Achiano *et al.* (1999) indicated that mixing wood ash with maize kernels before it is stored resulted in 100 per cent *S. zeamais* adult mortality after 20 days of treatment. Moreover, a

progressive increase in mortality with wood ash concentration was observed after 20 days. If added in sufficient quantity, wood ash can effectively protect grain stored in small lots by traditional Africa farmers (Golob *et al.*, 1982). They indicated that the quantity must be as much as 20 per cent or more, in order to submerge the grain almost completely. Moreover, the abrasive properties of the materials may play some part in preventing the development of pests; it is more likely that the dust inhibit insect behavior, affecting movement and reproduction by blocking air and space between grains. Wood ash also reduced enset root maly bug, however, at higher doses shocking effect on plant was observed (Unpublished data)

Locally available dusts will continue to play an important role as grain protectants in farm stores in African and other developing countries because they are readily available (Golob and Hanks, 1999; Eman, 1993). However, such practice will remain viable for small-scale use only, particularly for the preservation of small quantities of seed grains, because of excessive quantities of dust required and the implication of some quality problems.

S. cerealella

The effects of inert materials in the control of *S. cerealella* are presented in (Table 2). Among inert materials used, coffee husk at the rate of 20 per cent w/w followed by wood ash 15 and 30 per cent highly restricted the development of F1 progeny of *S. cerealella* compared to the untreated control. Saw dust was not better than the untreated control in all parameters except germination capacity. However, relatively lower number of F1 progeny and mean number of damaged kernels were recorded from higher rates of sawdust compared to the untreated control. All inert materials tested against the pest had a significant effect with regards to germination capacity of the maize kernels compared to the untreated control (Fig. 2). The highest germination percentage was recorded from kernels treated with wood ash 10 per cent w/w, while lowest germination percentage was recorded from untreated control.

There was significant difference among inert materials and pirimiphos-methyl treatments in all parameters. Sawdust in four dosages showed significantly inferior performance with regards to mean number of damaged kernels, germination capacity of the kernels and F1 progeny emergence. However, the highest dosage, 30 per cent w/w of wood ash was not

different from pirimiphos-methyl treatment. In suppressing the development of F1 progeny emergence of the pest, coffee husk at 20 per cent w/w and wood ash at 15 and 30 per cent w/w showed similar performance with that of pirimiphos-methyl. These rates of indicated inert materials also showed similar performance with regards to mean number of damaged kernels. Except sawdust at the rate of 10 per cent w/w, coffee husk at 10 per cent w/w and wood ash at the rate of 20 per cent w/w, all dosages of inert materials were not significantly different from pirimiphos-methyl treatment with regard to germination. In general, lowest F1 progeny and mean numbers of damaged kernels were recorded from kernels treated with Pirimiphos-methyl. The best performance of pirimiphos-methyl in restricting development of F1 progeny as compared to almost all inert materials evaluated in this study agrees with reports of previous researchers. Eman (1993) reported that the highest dose of the local materials such as wood ash and tobacco dust was better than the lowest dose in controlling *S. cerealella* except sawdust.

CONCLUSION

Locally available inert materials including sawdust, coffee husk and wood ash were evaluated at different proportions against *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella*. The efficacy of each treatment was evaluated with respect to F1 progeny emergence of the pests, mean number of damaged and germination percentage of maize seed. Coffee husk and wood ash at all dosages were found to be effective in controlling *S. zeamais* and *S. cerealella*. Wood ash at all proportions gave the best control of the pests during the study period. Wood ash and coffee husk at higher rates were more effective in controlling the pests. Sawdust at all dosages was not different from the untreated control in controlling *S. zeamais*. However, sawdust at some dosages showed superior performance against *S. cerealella*. Newly evaluated inert material like coffee husk should be re-tested to confirm the current result and sawdust, which showed inferior performance to the untreated control, should be tested at different environmental condition to confirm the result of the current study. In Ethiopia, where study was conducted especially, high dosage of saw dust applied treatments increased the F1 progeny emergence of weevil. This might be due to the increased temperature of the micro-environment of the treatments as observed during execution of the experiment.

Table 1: F1 progeny of *S. zeamais*, number of damaged maize kernels and weight loss as influenced by coffee husk inert materials, 2002

Treatments	Number of F1 progeny emerged	Number of damaged Kernels/500 kernels	% Weight loss
10% Coffee husk	107.00 ^{b-d}	114.33 ^{ed}	1.59 ^{b-e}
15% Coffee husk	109.33 ^{cd}	128.00 ^{b-d}	1.79 ^{b-e}
20% Coffee husk	65.67 ^{d-f}	80.00 ^{d-f}	1.12 ^{de}
30% Coffee husk	96.67 ^{c-e}	107.67 ^{c-e}	1.45 ^{c-e}
10% sawdust	121.00 ^{b-d}	130.67 ^{b-d}	3.38 ^{a-d}
15% sawdust	174.33 ^{a-c}	189.00 ^{a-c}	4.38 ^{a-c}
20% saw dust	247.33 ^a	244.33 ^a	4.40 ^{a-c}
30% sawdust	215.00 ^{ab}	227.67 ^{ab}	4.81 ^a
10% Wood ash	19.00 ^g	27.33 ^g	0.55 ^e
15%Wood ash	8.00 ^g	15.00 ^g	0.24 ^e
20% Wood ash	20.00 ^{fg}	29.33 ^{fg}	0.51 ^e
30% Wood ash	8.33 ^g	18.33 ^g	0.29 ^e
2% Pirimiphos-methyl	7.67 ^g	14.33 ^g	0.61 ^e
Untreated control	153.67 ^{a-d}	165.67 ^{a-d}	4.21 ^{ab}
SE (±)	2.28	0.90	0.24
CV%	23.22	7.96	27.37

All means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different from each other at 5% (DMRT). Statistical tests were made with transformed values

Key: SD=saw dust, WA=wood ash, CH=Coffee husk

Table 2. Effect coffee husk and inert materials on F1 progeny of *S. cerealella*, number of damaged maize kernels and weight loss, 2002

Treatments	Number of F1 Progeny emerged	Number of damaged kernels/500 seeds	%Weight loss
10% Coffee husk	66.67 ^{a-c}	70.00 ^{a-d}	0.95 ^{b-e}
15% Coffee husk	108.00 ^{ab}	114.67 ^{a-c}	1.92 ^{b-e}
20% Coffee husk	33.33 ^{cd}	36.00 ^{de}	0.54 ^{de}
30% Coffee husk	82.67 ^{a-c}	84.33 ^{a-d}	1.65 ^{c-e}
10% sawdust	73.33 ^{a-c}	75.67 ^{a-d}	1.80 ^{a-d}
15% sawdust	69.33 ^{a-c}	71.00 ^{a-d}	1.23 ^{a-c}
20% saw dust	109.00 ^{ab}	110.00 ^{ab}	2.04 ^{a-c}
30% sawdust	48.67 ^{a-d}	52.67 ^{a-d}	1.05 ^a
10% Wood ash	71.00 ^{a-c}	77.33 ^{a-d}	1.00 ^e
15%Wood ash	47.00 ^{b-d}	48.00 ^{b-c}	1.12 ^e
20% Wood ash	75.67 ^{a-c}	77.67 ^{a-d}	1.46 ^e
30% Wood ash	35.67 ^{b-d}	36.00 ^{c-e}	0.53 ^e
2% Pirimiphos-methyl	7.33 ^d	7.67 ^e	0.08 ^e
Untreated control	133.67 ^a	140.67 ^a	4.12 ^{ab}
SE (±)	1.35	1.37	0.17
CV%	30.08	29.75	22.64

All means followed by the same letter (s) within a column are not significantly different from each other at 5% (DMRT). Statistical tests were made with transformed values

REFERENCES

- Abraham, T. (1991). The Biology, significance and control of the maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: curculionidae) in maize. M. Sc. Thesis, Alemaya University of Agriculture, Alemaya, Ethiopia.
- Achiano, K. A., Giliomee, J. H. and Pringle, K. L. (1999). The use of ash from *Aloe marlothii* Berger for the control of maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) in stored maize. *African Entomology* 7: 169 - 172.
- Assefa, G. (1981). Some preliminary studies on the maize stalk borer, *Busseola fusca* (Fuller) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in southern Ethiopia. M.Sc. Thesis, Addis Ababa University, College of Agriculture. CSA (Central Statistical Authority) (2002). Agricultural sample survey 2000/2001. Report on area and production of major crops (Private peasant holdings, Belg season). *Statistical Bulletin No. 245*, CSA, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 76 pp.
- Dobie, P. (1974). The susceptibility of different types of maize to post-harvest infestation by *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Sitotroga cerealella* and the importance of this factor at the small-scale farm level. *Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de maizy Trigo, condeses* 40, Mexico 6 D.F. No. 10, 98 - 113.
- Emana, G. (1993). Studies on the distribution and control of Angoumois grain moth, *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Sidama administrative region. M. Sc. Thesis, Alemaya University of Agriculture, Alemaya, Ethiopia.
- Emana, G. (1999). Use of botanical plants in the control of stored maize grain insect pests in Ethiopia, 105 - 108 pp.. In: Maize Production Technology for the Future: Challenge and Opportunities: Proceedings of the Sixth Eastern and Southern Africa Regional Maize Conference, 21 - 25 September 1998, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Evans, N. J. (1985). The effectiveness of various insecticides on some resistant beetle pests of stored products from Uganda. *Journal of Stored Product Research* 21: 105 - 109.
- Firdissa, E. and Abraham, T. (1999). Effect of some botanicals and other materials against the maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky on stored maize, 101 - 104 pp.. In: Maize Production Technology for the Future: Challenge and Opportunities: Proceedings of the Sixth Eastern and Southern Africa Regional Maize Conference, 21 - 25 September 1998, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Golob, P., Mwambula, J. M., Mhango, V. and Ngulube, F. (1982). The use of locally available materials as protectants of maize grain and insect infestation during storage in Malawi. *Journal of Stored Product Research* 18: 67 - 74.
- Gwinner, J., Harnisch, R. and Muck, O. (1996). *Manual on the Prevention of Post-harvest Grain Losses*: Post harvest Project, FRG, Germany, 334 pp.

- Hodges, R. J. and Meik, J. (1986). Lethal and sub lethal effects of Permethrin on Tanzania strains of *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst), *Sitophilus oryzae* (Linnaeus) and *S. zeamais* Motschulsky. *Insect Science and its Application* 7: 533 - 537.
- Maceljski, M and Korunic, Z. (1972). Contribution to the knowledge of the mechanism of action of inert dusts on insects. *Zasista Belja* 22: 377 - 387.
- Wright, V. F., Millis, R. B. and Willcut, B. J. (1989). Methods for culturing stored grain insects, 74 - 83 pp.. *In: Towards Insect Resistance Maize for the Third World: Proceedings of the International Symposium on Methodologies for Developing Host Plant Resistance to Maize Insects*. CIMMYT, Mexico, 9 - 14 March 1987. CIMMYT: Mexico D.F.

Cite this Article: Gemu M, Getu E, Yosuf A and Tadesse T (2013). Management of *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Ciurculionidae) and *Sitotroga cerealella* (Olivier) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) using Locally Available Inert Materials in Southern Ethiopia. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 3(6): 503-510, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2013.6.052213635>.